

Synthesis and characterization of (η^6 -*p*-cymene) Ru^{II} complexes containing N, N O donor ligands and tertiary phosphines

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A series of ruthenium(II) complexes [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)L] (where L = Cl, pz, mpz, dmpz, idz, imz, bimz) and [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)L']BF₄ (where L' = PPh₃, Ph₂P-2-C₆H₄COOH, Ph₂P-3-C₆H₄COOH, Ph₂P-4-C₆H₄COOH, Ph₂P-2-C₆H₄N, Ph₂P-2-C₆H₄CHO and Ph₂PCH₂COOH) have been synthesized in a quantitative yield and characterized by analytical, IR, ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR and electronic spectral studies. The octahedral geometry has been tentatively proposed for all the new complexes. The electrochemical behaviour of these complexes were studied by cyclic voltammetry and observed that an irreversible single reduction wave Ru^{II} → Ru⁰ ranging from -0.5 to -1.6 volts indicating a single step two electron transfer process.

Synthesis and characterization of arene-ruthenium complexes have drawn special attention owing to their catalytic potential and their use of precursors for the synthesis of Ru⁰ and Ru^{II} complexes¹⁻⁴. The dimeric complex, [(η^6 -arene)RuCl₂]₂ undergoes bridge cleavage reaction upon treatment with various monodentate ligands L (where L = pyridine, pyrazole, triphenyl phosphine, etc.) to give monomeric complexes^{5,6} and further halide substitution may afford the cationic derivatives [(η^6 -arene)RuCl₂Cl]⁺ which depends on L and the solvent used^{7,8}. Reaction of [(η^6 -arene)RuCl₂]₂ with potentially bidentate ligands yielded complexes of the type [(η^6 -arene)RuCl₂]₂(μ -LL)^{9,10}. In an extension of our earlier studies on platinum group metals¹¹⁻¹³, we report the reactivity of [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)RuCl₂]₂ with N O donor bidentate 8-quinolinole and N donor monodentate pyrazole, 3,5-dimethyl pyrazole, indazole, imidazole, benzimidazole along with tertiary phosphines.

Results and discussion

The initial reaction between [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)RuCl₂]₂ and sodium salt of 8-quinolinol yields in the formation of crystalline complex **1** from which the compounds **2-7** were obtained by treating with sodium salt of pyrazolates and imidazole derivatives. Often, chloride substitution from complex **1** is carried out by introducing various tertiary phosphines in the presence of AgBF₄ and the corresponding cationic derivatives were isolated.

All the new (η^6 -*p*-cymene) ruthenium(II) organometallics synthesized in a quantitative yield are air-stable and

non-hygroscopic solids. These complexes are freely soluble in dichloromethane, ethanol, acetone, but insoluble in non-polar solvents. The analytical data for the new complexes is in good agreement with the proposed molecular formula (Table 1). The molar conductance values of the complexes **8-14** measured in acetone at room temperature ($\Lambda_M = 98-145$ cm² mho mol⁻¹) confirm their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The other complexes **1-7** were found to be non-electrolytes. All the Ru^{II} complexes **1-14** obtained were diamagnetic (low-spin *d*⁶, S = 0) and their diamagnetic nature was confirmed by ESR spectra where no signal was observed.

L	L'
(2) pz	(8) PPh ₃
(3) mpz	(9) Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH
(4) dmpz	(10) Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH
(5) idz	(11) Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH
(6) imdz	(12) Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N
(7) bimdz	(13) Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO
	(14) Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH

Fig. 1

Table 1. Analytical data for the (η^6 -*p*-cymene) Ru^{II} organometallics

Complex	Found (Calcd.) %		
	C	H	N
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Cl] (1)	53.82 (54.90)	4.69 (4.80)	3.32 (3.37)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)pz] (2)	58.42 (59.18)	4.91 (5.15)	9.22 (9.41)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)mpz] (3)	59.88 (59.99)	5.38 (5.43)	9.02 (9.12)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)dmpz] (4)	47.89 (48.09)	5.62 (5.69)	8.72 (8.85)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)idz] (5)	61.72 (62.89)	4.96 (5.03)	8.02 (8.06)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)imdz] (6)	58.90 (59.18)	5.02 (5.15)	9.38 (9.41)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)bimdz] (7)	61.42 (62.89)	4.89 (5.03)	7.98 (8.06)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)PPh ₃]BF ₄ (8)	59.88 (61.00)	4.69 (4.80)	1.90 (1.92)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH]BF ₄ (9)	59.06 (59.07)	4.48 (4.53)	1.70 (1.81)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH]BF ₄ (10)	58.88 (59.07)	4.42 (4.53)	1.75 (1.81)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH]BF ₄ (11)	58.92 (59.07)	4.49 (4.53)	1.79 (1.81)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N]BF ₄ (12)	59.18 (59.27)	4.62 (4.66)	3.82 (3.84)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO]BF ₄ (13)	60.10 (60.32)	4.58 (4.63)	1.82 (1.85)
[(η^6 - <i>p</i> -Cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ -COOH]BF ₄ (14)	55.58 (55.78)	4.64 (4.64)	1.92 (1.93)

In order to identify the binding mode of the ligands to ruthenium in the new complexes, the IR spectra of free ligands were compared with the spectra of the ruthenium complexes. The 8-quinolinol exhibited an absorption band at 3480 cm⁻¹ due to ν (OH), which disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes indicating the involvement of OH group in coordination¹⁴. This observation is further supported by disappearance of a band at 1380 cm⁻¹ due to δ (OH) in all the complexes. Thus, the bonding of the ruthenium metal ion to 8-quinolinolate takes place through covalent linkage with the phenolic oxygen. The band assigned to C=N group is shifted to lower frequency around 1600–1560 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of chelates which indicates the bonding of 8-quinolinolate through ring nitrogen. The spectra of all the 8-quinolinol chelates show a strong peak about 1095–1110 cm⁻¹ and ascribed to C–O stretching frequency at the C–O–M site¹⁴. A medium intensity absorption band found in the complexes of **2–7** in the region 1570–1550 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to N-bonded azole ring¹⁵.

The IR spectral data of cationic complexes **9**, **10**, **11** and **14** exhibit a strong absorption band around 1720 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to non-involvement of carboxylic group of tertiary phosphine in coordination. All the cationic complexes show two bands one around 1100–1090 and another 540–520 cm⁻¹ assigned to uncoordinated BF₄⁻ ion¹⁶. Further, these cationic complexes are studied in far IR region which show a new absorption band in the range 520–500 cm⁻¹ and attributed to ν (Ru–P)¹⁷. The far IR spectrum of complex **1** shows a medium band at 303 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to ν (Ru–Cl)¹⁸.

Further evidence for the presence of coordinated *p*-cymene, heterocyclics and tertiary phosphines in the new ruthenium(II) complexes is gained from the NMR spectra of the complexes. (Tables 2 and 3).

All the complexes invariably exhibit two doublet signals in the range of 5.15–5.86 ppm which are assigned to the H_A, H_B type methine protons of ruthenium coordinated *p*-cymene ring ($J_{(HH)}$ 6.0–6.2 Hz). Further, another singlet signal is observed in the range of 1.70–2.19 ppm which is ascribed to the methyl protons of tolyl group. In this continuation the septet signals are observed in the range of 2.79–2.92 ppm and assigned to methine proton of isopropyl group of *p*-cymene ring. One doublet signal is appeared for all the complexes in the range of 1.12–1.24 ppm ($J_{(HH)}$ 6.9–7.0 Hz) and attributed to methyl protons of isopropyl group of *p*-cymene ring. The appearance of only one sharp doublet signal for the protons of two methyl groups suggests that only a single product is formed⁹.

The resonance signal of pyrazole ring for 4-H of complexes **2**, **3** and **4** are observed at 6.10, 6.02, 5.98 ppm. From the above inspection it is observed that the 4-H resonance value of coordinated methyl pyrazole and 3,5-dimethyl pyrazole are in the upfield than the coordinated pyrazole. This may be happening due to the presence of electron releasing methyl groups on pyrazole ring¹⁹. The ¹H NMR spectra of cationic complexes **9**, **10**, **11** and **14** exhibit one sharp signal in the down field around 12.20 ppm, which is a characteristic signal for the uncoordinated carboxylic group of tertiary phosphine²⁰. The aromatic protons of vari-

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data of η^6 -*p*-cymene Ru^{II} organometallics

Complex	¹ H peak positions (δ ppm)						COOH (br)	Aryl (m)
	<i>p</i> Cymene							
	Toulyl CH ₃ (s)	Isopropyl CH ₃ (d) CH (sp)		Arene H _A (d) H _B (d)		Azole 4-H		
1	2.19	1.18	2.90	5.31	5.50	–	–	6.80–7.41
2	1.91	1.24	2.82	5.56	5.86	6.10 (t)	–	6.52–7.50
3	1.96	1.12	2.84	5.54	5.74	6.02 (d) 2.32 (s) ^a	–	6.62–7.44
4	1.74	1.14	2.77	5.50	5.78	5.98 (s) 2.30 (s) ^a 2.17 (s) ^a	–	6.50–7.43
5	2.00	1.20	2.92	5.34	5.56	–	–	6.80–7.56
6	1.94	1.16	2.82	5.56	5.86	–	–	6.50–7.54
7	1.96	1.12	2.80	5.54	5.84	–	–	6.86–7.84
8	2.08	1.14	2.89	5.38	5.50	–	–	6.83–8.84
9	1.88	1.17	2.84	5.54	5.86	–	12.10	6.80–7.82
10	1.84	1.16	2.86	5.38	5.52	–	12.14	6.82–7.86
11	1.86	1.12	2.86	5.15	5.36	–	12.20	6.80–7.85
12	2.06	1.15	2.88	5.34	5.52	–	–	6.84–7.86
13	1.98	1.18	2.84	5.36	5.54	–	10.65 ^b	6.82–7.84
14	2.04	1.16	2.97	5.54	5.86	–	11.96 3.65 (d) ^c	6.80–7.92

^aCH₃ of mpz, dmpz, ^b-CHO of Ph₂P-2-C₆H₄CHO, ^c-CH₂ of Ph₂P-2-CH₂COOH

s - singlet, d - doublet, t - triplet, sp - septet, m - multiplet, br - broad

Table 3. ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectral data η^6 -*p*-cymene Ru^{II} organometallics

Complex	¹³ C peak positions (δ ppm)										³¹ P peak positions (ppm)		
	<i>p</i> -Cymene								Azole	8-Quinolinol		COOH	Aryl
	Toulyl Me	Isopropyl Me CH		Arene C _A C _B C-Me C-pr ¹			C=C	C=N					
1	18.18	22.48	30.04	80.31	84.30	96.20	102.92	–	–	157.20	–	123.00–128.50	–
2	17.21	22.20	30.42	80.88	84.36	97.57	100.05	102.50	142.35	151.92	–	126.50–132.00	–
3	18.20	21.20	30.14	80.24	84.26	98.24	101.02	106.82	146.35	156.84	–	124.29–132.40	–
4	17.51	22.46	30.69	79.62	84.32	98.28	101.75	107.85	147.34	152.84	–	125.29–134.50	–
8	18.29	23.28	29.68	84.24	91.20	98.12	107.62	–	–	158.11	–	121.14–135.98	30.24
10	18.64	22.64	30.06	83.06	90.62	97.54	106.12	–	–	156.88	172.46	122.10–136.12	32.41
14	18.09	23.14	29.68	84.20	91.22	98.16	107.62	–	–	152.84	172.40	128.96–139.24	35.40

^aCH₃ of mpz and dmpz, ^b-CH₂ of Ph₂PCH₂COOH

ous environments present in the complexes are appeared as multiplets in the range of 6.80–7.80 ppm.

¹³C NMR signals for present series of Ru^{II} complexes

are assigned by the comparison with the spectra of corresponding free ligands. Such investigation of the chemical shifts in ¹³C NMR spectra reveals a consistent pattern. In

all instances the resonance of the C atoms which involved in coordination to the ruthenium metal are shifted ~20–30 ppm. *p*-Cymene ring methine carbons of C_A and C_B signals are detected for all the complexes in the range of 80.31–91.20 ppm. The characteristic signal for methyl carbon of tolyl group is observed in the range of 17.21–18.64 ppm and another signal in the range of 29.68–30.69 ppm which is ascribed to methine carbon of isopropyl group of *p*-cymene. The methyl carbon of isopropyl is also detected in the high field range of 22.20–22.64 ppm. Further, the ¹³C NMR signals are observed in the range of 96.20–98.28 and 100.05–108.20 ppm and assigned to the methyl attached carbon and isopropyl linked carbon of *p*-cymene ring, respectively.

All the complexes exhibit one down field signal in the range of 157–159 ppm for C=N of N-bonded 8-quinolinolate group. In addition to this another down field signal exhibited by these complexes in the range of 150 ppm, which is assigned to ArC–O. The ¹³C NMR spectra of complexes containing pyrazole (2), methyl pyrazole (3) and 3,5-dimethyl pyrazole (4) show the signals at 142.03, 146.34, 147.34 (C=N), 102.50, 106.82, 107.85 (C=C), respectively, of a N-bonded pyrazole ring. The variation in the values of ¹³C NMR signal resonances of C=C of pyrazole and its derivative complexes is arising due to the effect of shielding phenomena of methyl groups²¹.

Further, the ¹³C NMR spectra of cationic complexes 10–14 exhibit a signal in the range of 172–174 ppm which is assigned to the uncoordinated carboxylic group of tertiary phosphine¹⁷.

³¹P NMR spectra of all cationic complexes exhibit only one singlet signal in the down field region centered in the range of 30.24–35.40 ppm. The ³¹P chemical shifts are observed for Ru^{II} organometallics 8–14 in the down field as compared to that of the free ligands mainly due to the strong sigma donor bond from phosphorous to metal with small dπ–dπ back donation from the metal ion to phosphorous²².

The new η⁶-*p*-cymene ruthenium(II) organometallics are diamagnetic indicating the presence of ruthenium with +2 oxidation state, the ground state of ruthenium(II) (*t*_{2g}⁶ configuration) is ¹A_{1g}. The excited states corresponding to *t*_{2g}⁵ *e*_g¹ configuration are ³T_{1g}, ³T_{2g}, ¹T_{1g} and ¹T_{2g} in an increasing order of energy. Hence, four bands are possible corresponding to the ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions in an octahedral geometry.

Regarding charge transfer bands, no band due to L → M transitions are possible in the visible region of the low spin

*d*⁶ system because of the presence of *p*-cymene as a ligand capable of producing strong ligand field *e*_g levels which are relatively high in energy. As a result, the bands due to charge transfer transitions L → *e*_g^{*} or L_{ou} → *e*_g^{*} should be in the high energy region. Therefore, the lowest charge transfer band due to excitation of an electron from metal *t*_{2g} level to unfilled molecular orbital derived from the π* levels of the ligands (*t*_{2g} → *t*_{1u} or *t*_{2u}) should appear at a high energy region compared to those due to *t*_{2g} *e*_g^{*} transitions.

In the electronic spectra of all the ruthenium(II) complexes four bands are observed in the region 650–243 nm. The bands appeared around 650–610 nm, were assigned to the transition ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and bands appearing around 432–406 nm have been assigned to the transition ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g}. The other higher energy bands observed in the range 351–309, 258–243 nm are due to charge transfer transitions²³.

Electron transfer properties of Ru^{II} complexes have been studied in aqueous methanol by cyclic voltammetry. Complexes 1, 2, 3, 8 and 10 irreversibly reduce at potential values of –1.33, –1.36, –1.32, –1.20 and –1.05 respectively (vs Ag/AgCl), as the ligands used in the study are not reversibly reduced or oxidised within the potential limits.

The above mentioned complexes showed irreversible single reduction wave Ru^{II} to Ru⁰ ranging from –0.5 to –1.6 volts, indicating a single step two electron transfer process. The appearance of only one cathodic wave in the above mentioned potential range confirms the direct reduction from Ru^{II} to Ru⁰, without any evidence of the stabilization of Ru^I intermediates. Electrochemical investigations at different scan rates also produce only one cathodic wave, which suggests the reduction of Ru^{II} → Ru⁰ is a single step process and the plot constructed between square root of scan rate and peak current provide a straight line passing through the origin. This phenomenon reveals that electron transfer from Ru^{II} → Ru⁰ is a diffusion controlled process^{7,24}.

Conclusions :

The reactivity of heterocyclic viz. nitrogen donor ligands with complex 1 affords neutral complexes 2–7 quantitatively by the displacement of chloride. On the other hand cationic complexes 8–14 were isolated by the reaction of complex 1 with tertiary phosphines. On the basis of spectral data the octahedral geometry is tentatively proposed for all these complexes, [(η⁶-*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)L] and [(η⁶-*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)L']BF₄ and shown in Fig. 1.

An investigation of the cyclic voltammograms of these complexes shows that it undergoes an irreversible direct reduction from Ru^{II} \rightarrow Ru⁰ which may be utilized in catalytic applications.

Experimental

Commercially available RuCl₃·3H₂O was used as supplied. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard procedures²⁵. Microanalyses of the complexes were performed on a PE 240 C model elemental analyser, Technical University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany. Infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 instrument in KBr pellets in the 4000–200 cm⁻¹ range. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in dichloromethane using a Shimadzu MPS-5000 instrument in the 1000–200 nm range. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker WH 270 instrument using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra and ³¹P NMR spectra of all the complexes were recorded on a Bruker WH 270 (109–29 MHz) instrument. Molar conductances (Λ_M) were measured in a Systronics conductivity meter 305 model using $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution in acetone. Electrochemical measurements were made in aqueous methanol using PAR model 264 A3 polarographic analyzer. The three electrodes were stationary mercury drop working electrode (SMDE), platinum wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and uncorrected for junction potentials.

All the reactions are carried out in an inert atmosphere using Schlenk technique. The precursor [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)RuCl₂]₂ and tertiary phosphines are prepared according to published procedures^{18,20,26} and used for the synthesis of new ruthenium(II) organometallics.

Neutral ruthenium(II) complexes [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Cl] (1) : A 100 ml round bottomed flask containing a magnetic stirring bar was charged with suspension of [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)RuCl₂]₂ (0.306 g, 0.5 mmol) in acetone (20 ml). The addition of a solution of sodium salt of 8-quinolinolate (0.167 g, 1.0 mmol) in acetone (15 ml) gave to the immediate change in the colour of the solution from red to orange. After being stirred for 1 h at room temperature, the solvent volume was reduced in a rotary evaporator. Then 10 ml of diethyl ether was added to the solution, after which the orange crystalline solid was collected quantitatively by filtration using a fine sintered-glass filter washed with ether and vacuum dried. Yield : 83.9%, 0.397 g.

The other neutral complexes **2-7** were prepared in good yields (84–87%) adopting the similar procedure by the dis-

placement of chloride on interaction of pyrazole, methylpyrazole, dimethylpyrazole, indazole, imidazole and benzimidazole with [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Cl] (**1**).

Cationic ruthenium(II) complexes [(η^6 -*p*-cymene-Ru(8-quin-O)PPh₃)]BF₄ (8) : To a solution of [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(8-quin-O)Cl] (0.206 g, 0.5 mmol) in acetone (20 ml), AgBF₄ (0.097 g, 0.5 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 0.25 h and then filtered to remove the formed AgCl precipitate. Tertiary phosphine (0.131 g, 0.5 mmol) was added to the above filtrate, the resulting solution was stirred for 2 h and then concentrated to 5 ml under reduced pressure. Diethyl ether was added to the above brown colour solution to obtain the brown crystalline compound, it was then washed with ether and dried in vacuo. Yield : 78%, 0.263 g.

The analogous complexes **9-14** were obtained by the same method in a quantitative yield (78–89%). All the complexes were recrystallized from dichloromethane and diethyl ether mixture.

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